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Research Article

DISPARITIES IN QUALITY OF LIFE AND PROBLEMS SUFFERED BY AGED PEOPLE LIVING IN THE AREAS OF ISLAMABAD AND RAWALPINDI

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Abstract:

Objective: The main purpose of this research work is to assess the troubles suffered and disparities in QOC (quality of life) between the aged people of three adjacent areas of two close big cities of Pakistan.

Setting and period: This research work carried out in 3 areas around the cities of Islamabad & Rawalpindi in a period of 6 months from August 2018 to the end of February 2019.

Methodology: One hundred ten people were the participants of this research work, in which fifty-five were females and fifty five were male participants. This transverse case study conducted on the population having more than sixty year of age. People having any serious abnormality and mental or physical abnormality were not the part of this research work. In this research work, we utilized the instruments of QOC created by World Health Organization which updated and mostly used methods in the research of QOC. All the participants gave their consent before the start of the research work. Information collection from all the people carried out with the help of interviews & analysis of the collected information carried out with the help of SPSS software version twenty one.

Results: Fifty eight people were from sixty to sixty four year of age. Thirty nine participants were in the age group of sixty five to sixty nine year of age. Forty one people had no qualification. Sixty three participants were living in the joint family system. Forty nine participants were from the families having monthly salary of sixteen thousand to twenty five thousand while twenty participants' families having the monthly income of twenty six to thirty five thousand. Most of the samples were depending on their offspring. Twenty four samples were facing financial problems while twenty two were the victims of loneliness. Sixty eight samples described that the attitude of their family was very friendly & courteously with them. The score of QOL for physical health, mental health, public relations & atmosphere were considerably greater in men as compare to the women. The total QOC depending upon the score of QOC was appreciably better in men samples as compared to women samples.

Conclusions: The overall QOC on the basis of QOC score was best in men samples as compared to female samples. Their hectic children or family clashes & misunderstandings initiate their unhappy moments of aged life.

Keywords: Sample, participants, QOC, aged, abnormality, financial, problem, adjacent.

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INTRODUCTION:

Aging is an incidence which cannot be preventable. The elaboration of advanced age is as a period in which human being depends upon the help of others in most of their life matters. The high amount of the aged population is creating serious problems health care fields, especially psychological services [1, 2]. About 12.3% population of the world was with age of sixty or above in 2015 and it will increase to 21.5% in 2050 [3, 4]. Pakistan with one hundred and eighty million populations & 0.75 ratio of dependency has burden of chronic disease attributing forty two percent of all deaths [5, 6]. The high inclination in the enlargement in aged population is available in the whole world but this rate is very high in the Asian countries due to the advancement in the field of medicines [7].

The aged population faces many health problems in which diabetes mellitus, hypertension & diseases of heart [8]. These diseases initiate many side effects which increase the distress and anxiety among aged people [9]. Aging initiates a lot of alterations in the arrangement of livings in the lives of old people [10]. Our religion Islam made it an obligation to respect elders as well as parents. Allah will give reward in turn in your older age [11]. The research on the elderly people conducted to make policies for the improvement of their quality of life [13]. This research work carried out to see the QoL of aged people of our society with a special focus on their mental & physical health.

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work carried out in three various nonurban regions near Rawalpindi & Islamabad and the duration of this research work was from August 2018 to February 2019. Snowball sampling method utilized for the selection of 110 people. The WHO calculator of sample size utilized for the calculation of the size of sample. The low QoL rate was 7.710% according to the scores of QoL mentioned by WHO [13] and level of precision as 5.0%. The aged people having any serious disease or mental or physical complications were not the part of this research work.

We utilized the instruments of QoL created by world health organization in this research work. Every person gave his consent before the start of this research work. Interviews carried out for the collection of the information from every patient. Open ended & close ended questions were in use at the time of interrogation. The classification of physical, mental, social associations & factors of environment scores of quality of life separated into 3 type's high, middle & low based on the attained scores. The three levels of QoL based on scores are;

1. Low level from 26 to 60 points,
2. Middle level from 61 to 95 points,
3. High level 130 points

SPSS .21 was in use for the analysis of collected information. For the calculation of average & standard deviation of the frequencies & the variables, descriptive statistics was in utilization. T test was in use for the comparison of the data. P value of less than 0.05 was significant.

RESULTS:

Exact 55 males & 55 females were the participants of this research work. Fifty eight aged people were in the age group of 60 to 64 years, 39 had the age of 65 to 69 years and only thirteen patients had the age of seventy years or above. Forty one aged people were not educated. Only eleven people had the qualification of graduate or above and all others had less qualification. About 57.270% participants of this research work were living in EFS (extended family system) while 42.730% people were spending their lives in NFS (nuclear family system). About 49 samples were from the families having a 16000 to 25000 rupees monthly income, 25 samples were from the families with 26000 to 35000 rupees monthly income. Sixteen families were available with monthly income of higher than 35000 rupees. Only twenty families were available with monthly income of less than 15000 rupees. The demographic characteristics an income source of all the samples is present in Table1A and 1B respectively.

Table 1A: Distribution of demographic characteristics of study sample

Variables		Males		Females		Total	
		n	%ag	n	%ag	n	%ag
Age in categories	60-64	30	54.54	28	50.91	58	52.73
	65-69	18	32.73	21	38.18	39	35.45
	70 and above	7	12.73	6	10.91	13	11.82
Educational Status	Illiterate	17	30.9	24	43.64	41	37.27
	Primary & Middle	26	47.27	19	34.54	45	40.91
	Matric & Intermediate	8	14.54	3	5.45	11	10
	Graduate and above	4	7.27	9	16.36	13	11.82
Family System	Nuclear	21	38.18	26	47.27	47	42.77
	Extended	34	61.82	29	52.73	63	57.27

Table 1B: Income Details

		Male		Female		Total	
		n	%age	n	%age	n	%age
Family Income Per Month	< 15000	8	14.54	12	21.82	20	18.18
	16000-25000	21	38.18	28	50.91	49	44.55
	26000-35000	16	29.1	9	16.36	25	22.73
	> 35000	10	18.18	6	10.91	16	14.54
Main Source of Income	Pension	8	14.54	12	21.82	20	18.18
	Dependent on children	12	21.82	19	34.54	31	28.18
	Business	11	20	5	9.1	16	14.54
	Own laboring	18	32.72	12	21.82	30	27.27
	Property	6	10.91	7	12.73	13	11.82

Thirty people thought that they are the responsibility of their family, 16 aged people were suffering from the condition of inferiority complex. About 24 people were facing the financial problems, 22 were facing loneliness & 19 found with health problems. About 68

people responded that the attitude of their family members is very polite with them but 46 people found with the opposite opinions as mentioned in Table2. The QoL of the aged males was better than the QoL of the female participants of the research work.

Table II: Family status and problems

Variables		Males		Females		Total	
		n	%age	n	%age	n	%age
Social Position in the family	Respect	9	16.36	14	25.45	23	20.91
	Sense of security	7	12.73	11	20	18	16.36
	Attention by family members	10	18.18	13	23.64	23	20.91
	Inferiority Complex	11	20	5	9.1	16	14.54
	Liability on family	18	32.73	12	21.82	30	27.27
Type of Problem faced	Financial	14	25.45	10	18.18	24	21.82
	Health	8	14.54	11	20	19	17.27
	Housing & Living condition	5	9.1	8	14.54	13	11.82
	Transport / Mobility	4	7.27	6	10.91	10	9.1
	Loneliness	12	21.82	10	18.18	22	20
	Recreational	4	7.27	5	9.1	9	8.18
	Conflict (with in laws)	3	5.45	2	3.64	5	4.55
	Timely Diet	5	9.1	3	5.45	8	7.27
Type of Behavior of family members	Friendly	32	58.18	36	58.18	68	61.82
	Unfriendly	23	41.82	23	41.82	46	41.82

The overall scores quality of life was considerably greater in the males as compared to the females on the basis of the QoL scores as mentioned elaborately in Table-3.

	Males		Females		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Physical Health	22.140	364.0	20.540	307.0	0.0140
Psychological Health	19.140	344.0	17.890	284.0	0.0400
Social Relationship	12.210	205.0	11.190	195.0	0.0090
Environment	26.350	383.0	24.780	314.0	0.0210
Overall QoL score	69.460	8.8	63.360	9.2	0.0010

DISCUSSION:

Aging has 3 major stages childhood, youngness & older age. This is a natural and biological process which is inevitable and government should give attention in making of policies. The quantity of the elderly people are increasing day by day with the upgradation in the medical field. Pakistan is also facing problems in this issue due to limited economic resources. The miserable life of the aged people is the result of the irresponsibility of the government [10, 14] It is the responsibility of the state to provide the basic needs of the elder peoples but is impractical in our country. The availability of the robust & total support of the family can compensate the population of the aged people [15]. Most of the elderly people are facing many issues of mistreatments [12, 16].

Even offspring do not support their aged parents to take visits & company of their close friends or relatives [17, 18]. The results of this research work displayed that quality of life of elderly males was greater than the aged females. This result is same the findings of other research works of different other countries. The case study of Apidechkul in the year of 2011 on aged people of nonurban areas of Thailand displayed that the amount of the aged females with less QoL was very high as compared to the aged males [19]. This result is very much similar to the findings of this research work as well as the previous studies [20]. Luong DH in his research work concluded that mean scores was high in males as 64.1 ± 10.4 as compared to the females as 61.0 ± 10.1 [21]. Some research reports of Nilsson on aged people of nonurban areas of Bangladesh concluded the same results [22, 23]. Our results were similar to the findings of study of Nilsson [23]. Pakistan has many problems as poverty and most of the aged people are

to suffer from these issues. But in current times expectancy of the life of females is increasing than the expectancy of the life of males [24]. The problem of compensating the requirements & the demands of severe increase in the aged people wants better administration and improvements for the social security of our state Pakistan [25].

CONCLUSIONS:

The quality of life was best in the male samples as compared to the female samples on the basis of the QOC scores. The initiation of the discontentment in the life the aged people is the result of the clashes of the family & misunderstandings.

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